

Polarographic study of In^{III} complexes with some amino acids (alanine and serine) and phthalic acid

Chanchal Karadia and O. D. Gupta*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 055, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : gupta_od@yahoo.co.in, chanchalkaradia@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 18 May 2009, revised 26 August 2010, accepted 15 September 2010

Abstract : A polarographic study of In^{III} with some amino acids (alanine (Ala) and serine (Ser)) and phthalic acid (PA) have been carried out separately at ionic strength kept constant ($\mu = 1$) by using KCl at 298 K. The reduction of all the systems have been found to be quasi-reversible and diffusion controlled involving three electrons. The stability constants were determined for the simple system of In^{III} with PA and In^{III} with amino acids first by method of DeFord and Hume and then the stability constants of mixed ligand complexes have been evaluated by the method of Schaap and McMaster.

Keywords : In^{III} , phthalic acid, L-alanine, L-serine, stability constants, mixed ligand complexes, polarographic study, quasi-reversible reduction.

Introduction

Mixed ligand complexes are formed in solutions containing metal ion with two or more different ligands. Polarography plays very important role in identification of mixed ligand complexes of different kinds. Andreoli, Sexena, Mazumdar and coworkers¹⁻⁴ have studied biologically active metal complexes of amino acid, which are important in analytical, biochemical and pharmaceutical fields⁵⁻⁷ and attract wide attention in different fields of research. Most of the earlier studied on mixed ligand complexes are of spectrophotometer measurements^{8,9}. Mixed ligand complexes of Rb and Cs metal salts of some organic acids have been studied by Prakash, Gupta, Kumar and Yadav¹⁰⁻¹². Stability constants of mixed ligand complexes of Cd^{II} and Cu^{II} have been studied by Chauhan, Verma and Paliwal¹³⁻¹⁶. The study of ternary complexes of different metal ions with amino acids and bicarboxylic acids have been carried out by Malhotra, Chandel and Singh¹⁷⁻²⁰.

Study of biologically important ligands with different metals and their ability of complexation have been carried out by Singh and Chandel^{21,22}. Verma, Singh and Chandel^{21,22} studied the stability constants of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ion with amino acids and some bicarboxylic acids at DME²³⁻²⁶.

The survey of literature reveals that there is lack of data on the mixed ligand complexes of In^{III} ion with amino acids (alanine and serine) and PA. Hence the present work has been undertaken for the study.

Results and discussion

Simple systems :

The stability constants of In^{III} with PA and amino acids (alanine and serine) were determined by the method of DeFord and Hume²⁷. The values of formation constants of simple systems are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Stability constants of In^{III} with PA and amino acids

System	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$
In-phthalic acid	1.675	2.729	4.338
In-alanine	5.218	5.944	7.544
In-serine	3.103	4.124	5.612

Mixed systems :

The maximum co-ordination number of indium is six $[\text{In}(\text{PA})(\text{amino acid})]$, $[\text{In}(\text{PA})(\text{amino acids})_2]$ and $[\text{In}(\text{PA})_2(\text{amino acid})]$ complexes would be expected with the two different bidentate ligands. In all the systems solution containing 1.0 mM In^{III} , 1 M KCl was used. The two values (0.04 M and 0.2 M) of weaker ligand (PA) at constant concentration were used to study the mixed sys-

tem of In-PA-amino acids, while varying the concentration of the second ligand (amino acid) in each case. The slope of the straight line was 40 mV for the plot of E_{de} vs $\log i/i_d - i$ in each case showing that the three electron reduction is quasi-reversible.

Different polarographic waves with increasing concentration of ligand (amino acid) in solution for In-alanine-phthalate system and In-serine-phthalate system at 0.04 M and 0.2 M mixed concentration of phthalic acid are shown in Figs. a, b, c and d, respectively.

Fig. a. In-alanine-phthalate system at 0.04 M fixed concentration of phthalic acid.

Fig. b. In-alanine-phthalate system at 0.2 M fixed concentration of phthalic acid.

In the presence of weaker ligand (PA) there is a greater shift in half wave potential than in its absence. It favoured mixed ligand complex formation. The extended Schaap and McMasters treatment was applied to the $E_{1/2}$ data and $F_{10}[X, Y]$ function and Lendend's graphical extrapolation method was applied to calculate A, B, C and D^{28,29}. A, B, C and D are constants and defined as :

$$A = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01} [(X)] + \beta_{02} [(Y)]^2 + \beta_{03} [(Y)]^3$$

Fig. c. In-serine-phthalate system at 0.04 M fixed concentration of phthalic acid.

Fig. d. In-serine-phthalate system at 0.2 M fixed concentration of phthalic acid.

$$B = \beta_{10} + \beta_{11} [(Y)] + \beta_{12} [(Y)]^2$$

$$C = \beta_{20} + \beta_{21} [(Y)]$$

$$D = \beta_{30}$$

A plot of $F_{00}(X, Y)$ vs $[X]$ results in a curve intercepting $F_{00}(X, Y)$ axis at 'A'. A similar plot of $F_{10}(X, Y)$ vs $[X]$ yields 'B' as intercept and 'C' is found graphically from the $F_{20}(X, Y)$ function 'D' is obtained by plotting $F_{30}(X, Y)$ vs $[X]$ as intercept.

The values of A, B, C and D at two fixed concentrations (0.04 M and 0.2 M) of phthalic acid were obtained and were shown in Figs. 1 and 2 for In-alanine-phthalate system and in Figs. 3 and 4 for In-serine-phthalate system.

The stability constants β_{11} and β_{12} were calculated by using two values of β at two different concentrations and two values of C gave two values of β_{21} which well agree with each other. The mean value of D is in well agree-

Fig. 1. Plots of $F_j(X)$ vs C_x for the In^{III} -(DL-alanine)-(phthalic acid) system at 298 K with fixed concentration = 0.04 M (phthalic acid).

Fig. 3. Plots of $F_j(X)$ vs C_x for the In^{III} -(L-serine)-(phthalic acid) system at 298 K with fixed concentration = 0.04 M (phthalic acid).

Fig. 2. Plots of $F_j(X)$ vs C_x for the In^{III} -(DL-alanine)-(phthalic acid) system at 298 K with fixed concentration = 0.2 M (phthalic acid).

Fig. 4. Plots of $F_j(X)$ vs C_x for the In^{III} -(L-serine)-(phthalic acid) system at 298 K with fixed concentration = 0.2 M (phthalic acid).

ment with the $\log \beta_{30}$. Values are given in the form of Tables 2 to 4.

The Schemes 1 and 2 represent the results where the log values of the equilibrium constants are numerical.

Schemes 1 and 2 can interpret the mixed ligand complex formation. Entropy and electrostatic effects must be related to the largest part of the difference in log K therefore, charged complexes formed.

Table 2. Values of A, B, C and D for In-PA-amino acids systems (PA concentration = 0.04 M)

System	log A	log B	log C	log D
In-PA-alaninate	1.812	5.246	6.392	7.556
In-PA-serinate	0.146	3.246	4.147	5.591

Amino acids have a tendency to be added with $[\text{In}(\text{PA})]$ and $[\text{In}(\text{amino acid})]$ which can be compared.

Table 3. Values of A, B, C and D for In-PA-amino acids systems (PA concentration = 0.2 M)

System	log A	log B	log C	log D
In-PA-alaninate	2.041	5.440	6.945	7.568
In-PA-serinate	0.531	3.959	4.491	5.602

Table 4. Stability constants of mixed ligand complexes of In-PA-amino acids system

System	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
In-PA-alaninate	5.311	6.240	7.598
In-PA-serinate	3.750	5.225	5.644

Scheme 1. In-PA-alaninate.

Scheme 2. In-PA-serinate.

Preference of the mixed ligand complexation can be explained by the addition of PA with In(amino acids) and In(PA) and the log K values (0.726, 0.93) and (1.021, 0.647) for indium-PA-alaninate and indium-PA-serinate systems, respectively.

The formation of the metal weaker ligand [In(PA)]

and metal stronger ligand [In(amino acid)] complexes by adding a weaker ligand (PA) can be interpreted with log K values (1.054, 3.636) and (1.054, 2.075) for the systems of indium-PA-alaninate and indium-PA-serinate respectively.

The addition of the PA to In(PA)₂, In(PA, amino acid) and In (amino acid) can be described by the help of log K (1.609, 0.929, 1.654) and (1.609, 1.475, 1.52) for indium-PA-alaninate and indium-PA-serinate, respectively and indicates that addition of bicarboxylic acids are preferred to a weaker ligand.

The log K values for addition of (PA) to In(PA)₂, In(amino acids, PA) and In(amino acids)₂ are (1.609, 0.929, 1.654) and (1.609, 1.475, 1.52) complexes respectively showing that addition of phthalate ion is preferred.

[In(amino acid)₂(PA)] are more stable than [In(amino acid)₃] complexes because the values of β_{21} are higher than β_{30} .

The disproportionation constant K can be used to express the tendency of formation of simple and mixed ligand complexes for the equilibrium.

$$2[\text{In(amino acid)(PA)}] = \text{In(amino acid)}_2 + \text{In(PA)}_2$$

Calculation of the disproportion constants can be made by the equations.

$$\log X_{11} = 2 \log \beta_{11} - (\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02})$$

$$\log X_{12} = 3 \log \beta_{12} - (\log \beta_{30} + 2 \log \beta_{03})$$

$$\log X_{21} = 3 \log \beta_{21} - (2 \log \beta_{30} + \log \beta_{03})$$

The calculated values of the log X₁₁, log X₁₂ and log X₂₁ are (1.948, 2.498 and 3.367) and (0.646, 1.409 and 1.417) for indium-PA-alaninate and indium-PA-serinate respectively. These reveal that all the ternary complexes are more stable.

The $\Delta \log K$ values can be calculated from the equations.

$$\Delta \log K_{11} = \log \beta_{11} - (\log \beta_{10} + \log \beta_{01})$$

$$\Delta \log K_{12} = \log \beta_{12} - (\log \beta_{10} + \log \beta_{02})$$

$$\Delta \log K_{21} = \log \beta_{21} - (\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{01})$$

The values of $\Delta \log K_{11}$, $\Delta \log K_{12}$ and $\Delta \log K_{21}$, are (-1.58, -1.7 and -0.021) and (-0.028, -0.607 and -0.155) for indium-PA-alaninate and indium-PA-serinate respectively. Higher values of $\Delta \log K$ proved that the ternary

complexes are more stable than expected from the statistical reasons.

The mixing constants are introduced for comparing the stability of simple and mixed ligand complexes.

$$K_m = \frac{\beta_{11}}{(\beta_{02}, \beta_{20})^{1/2}}$$

and the stabilization constants

$$\log K_s = \log K_m - \log_2$$

The log K_m values are (0.974 and 0.323) and log K_s values are (0.673 and 0.022) for indium-PA-alaninate and indium-PA-serinate respectively. The values of mixing and stabilization constant reveals that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes. The values of log K_m and log K_s are tabulated in Table 5.

Table 5. Values of the mixing constant (log K_m) and stabilization constant (log K_s) for indium-PA-amino acids systems

System	log K_m	log K_s
In-PA-alaninate	0.974	0.673
In-PA-serinate	0.323	0.022

Experimental

The test solutions were prepared in measuring flasks of Pyrex glass using conductivity water. The solutions contain 1.0 mM of In^{III} with varying concentrations of strong ligands (alanine and serine) and fixed concentration of weak ligand (PA). KCl used as supporting electrolyte to maintain the ionic strength of the solution at 1.0 M. The temperatures was maintained constant within ± 0.1 °C variation by using ultra Haake type Thermostat, KCl saturated calomel electrode, copper connecting wires and potentiometer was used. The test solution was placed in an H-type cell coupled with S.C.E. through an agar-agar, saturated KCl salt bridge. Prior to polarographic examination purified nitrogen was streamed through the test solution for the 10 min to remove the dissolved oxygen. The current variation as a function of applied potential was then plotted to obtain the polarogram. The capillary of the polarograph is having the following characteristics at height of mercury column (h_{Hg}) of 95 cm.

$$m = 4.66 \text{ mg/s}$$

$$t = 3 \text{ s (in open circuit)}$$

The tentative structure of metal complexes are shown below :

[1:1:1 complex]

[1:1:2 complex]

[1:2:1 complex]

[In^{III}-phthalic acid-alaninate] complexes

[1:1:1 complex]

[1:1:2 complex]

[1:2:1 complex]

[In^{III}-phthalic acid-serinate] complexes

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (Chanchal Karadia) is thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, for providing the laboratory facilities to carry out this research work and to CSIR for the award of SRF (NET).

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